

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Taxonomic revision and checklist of the family (Lamiaceae) in Iraq

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Abstract

The Lamiaceae L. family grows and widely distributed in Iraq. The study aimed to enumerate the species that has been preserved in several botanical herbariums: National Herbarium of Iraq- Ministry of Agriculture (BAG), University of Baghdad Herbarium (BUH), Iraq Natural History Research Center& Museum- University of Baghdad Herbarium (BUNH), College of Agricultural Engineering- University of Baghdad Herbarium (BUG), College of Agricultural Engineering Sciences- Duhok Province University Herbarium (DPUH) and College of Science - Salahddin University Herbarium (SUH). This family has not yet been registered in the Flora of Iraq. After examining more than 1000 herbarium specimens, the study found 139 species belonging to 33 genera have been reported in these herbariums. Upon comparing these taxa on <https://www.worldfloraonline.org/>, the study discovered that some genera and species were reported as synonyms, while other species were reported as unchecked and waiting taxonomic scrutiny in WFO org. database. Therefore, the remaining 103 species were reported as accepted species. The taxonomic status and distribution of Lamiaceae plants were also provided.

Keywords: Checklist; Herbarium; Iraq; Lamiaceae; Taxonomic status

1. Introduction

Lamiaceae belongs to the order Lamiales, it is a major group in Angiosperms and was first published as an accepted name in *Tekhno- Bot. Solvar* 355, 1820 (3 Aug. 1820) with 232 subordinate taxa [1], while [2] reported that Lamiaceae included 225 accepted genera. [3] mentioned that there are 31 general and more than 150 species growing in Iraq. Most of these genera distributed in the northern districts of Iraq, [4]. The researchers in Iraq have shown considerable interest in this family due to the wild distribution and the medical and ornamental (aesthetic) characteristics of its plants, as mentioned in some of these studies in the references [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16]. The study also provides an update on the taxonomic status and distribution of Lamiaceae plants.

2. Material and methods

The study examined all the specimens of Lamiaceae plants that collected over years and preserved in different herbariums in Baghdad and other provinces. The examination included: National Herbarium of Iraq- Ministry of Agriculture (BAG), University of Baghdad Herbarium (BUH), Iraq Natural History Research Center& Museum- University of Baghdad Herbarium (BUNH), College of Agricultural Engineering- University of Baghdad Herbarium (BUG), College of Agricultural Engineering Sciences- Duhok Province University Herbarium (DPUH) and College of Science - Salahddin University Herbarium (SUH). Then the scientific names were checked with the <https://worldfloraonline.org/> over three years; (21 October 2022), (23 Dec 2023) and (10 October 2024) following the updating of the taxonomic status as much as it possible and the distribution of the genera was determined from the herbarium specimens.

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3. Results

The plants of the Lamiaceae family grow in different district of Iraq; some are found in a single district, while others are distributed across multiple districts. *Coleus* Benth., *Cyclotrichium* Manden. & Scheng., *Hymenocrater* Fisch. & C.A.Mey., *Lagochilus* Bunge ex Benth. and *Peutapleura* Hand. - Mazz. have been found in one different district but plants of *Salvia* L. were collected from 14 different districts. The herbarium specimens of *Teucrium* L. included plants from 13 different districts. *Vetix* L. and *Ziziphora* L. were distributed across 10 districts. The plants of Lamiaceae thrive in areas with good humidity and low temperature, which is why most of the genera were collected near water and under trees in neglected area in the North of Iraq, as indicated in the labels of the herbarium specimens. The study found that some districts are rich in Lamiaceae plants, while others are not. There were 29 genera distributed in the MRO district and 28 genera in the MAM district within the Mountain region, while only two genera were collected from the LSM district within the Desert plateau region and four genera from the LBA district within the lower Mesopotamia region. The remaining genera fall within these distributions. (table 1), (map 1).

Table 1 The geographical distribution of the genera in Iraq

Genus	Districts of plant distribution in Iraq*
<i>Ajuga</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, MJS, DWD, LEA
<i>Ballota</i> L.	MRO, MSU, DWD
<i>Calamintha</i> Mill.	MAM, MRO, MJS
<i>Clinopodium</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, MJS
<i>Coleus</i> Lour.	LCA
<i>Cyclotrichium</i> (Boiss.) Manden. & sceng.	MAM, MRO, MSU, MJS
<i>Eremostachys</i> Bunge	MAM, MRO, MSU, FKI, DWD
<i>Hymenocrater</i> Fisch. & C.A.Mey.	MSU
<i>Lagochilus</i> Bunge ex Benth.	MSU
<i>Lallemantia</i> Fisch. & C.A.Mey.	MAM, MRO, MSU, MJS, FUJ, FNI, DLJ, DWD, DSD, LCA
<i>Lamium</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, MJS, FUJ, FNI, DWD, LCA, LEA
<i>Lycopus</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, FNI, FPF, LSM
<i>Marrubium</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, MJS, FUJ, FKI, FPF, DGA, DWD, DSD, LCA
<i>Melissa</i> L.	MAM, MRO, FPF, LEA, LCA
<i>Mentha</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, FUJ, FNI, FPF, LEA, LCA, LSM, LBA
<i>Micromeria</i> Benth.	MAM, MRO, MSU, FNI
<i>Moluccella</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, MJS, FUJ, FNI, DWD
<i>Nepeta</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, MJS
<i>Ocimum</i> L.	MRO, FUJ, LCA, LBA
<i>Origanum</i> L.	MAM, MRO, LCA
<i>Pentapleura</i> Hand.- Mazz.	MAM
<i>Phlomis</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, MJS, FUJ, FNI, FAR, FKI, FPF
<i>Prunella</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU
<i>Salvia</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, MJS, FUJ, FNI, FKI, FPF, DLJ, DGA, DWD, DSD, LEA, LCA
<i>Sideritis</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MJS
<i>Satureja</i> L.	MAM, MRO

<i>Scutellaria</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, MJS
<i>Stachys</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, MJS, FUJ, FNI, LCA
<i>Teucrium</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, FNI, FKI, FPF, DLJ, DGA, DWD, DSD, LEA, LCA, LBA
<i>Tapeinanthus</i> Herb.	DGA, DWD
<i>Thymus</i> L.	MAM, MRO, FNI, FAR
<i>Thymbra</i> Mill.	MAM, MRO, MSU, DWD, DSD
<i>Vetix</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, FUJ, FKI, FPF, DWD, DSD, LCA, LBA
<i>Ziziphora</i> L.	MAM, MRO, MSU, MJS, FUJ, FAR, FKI, FPF, DLJ, DWD

Figure 1 Physiological regions and districts of Iraq at [4]

The plants preserved in the mentioned herbariums represented 33 genera, including 149 species. After checking the herbarium specimens and the scientific names with World Flora Online (WFO), the study found that the genus *Coleus* L. has 21 synonyms and *Salvia* L. has 58 synonyms. However, most of the genera have synonyms ranged from 1 to 17, while four genera reported as synonyms; *Calamintha* Mill., *Eremostachys* Bunge and *Tapeinanthus* Herb and *Thymbra* Mill. therefore, their species were not confirmed by WFO as accepted scientific names. (table 2)

Table 2 Taxonomic status the species that reserved in some herbariums in Iraq

The genera	Link of Taxonomic status of the genera	Taxonomic status on WFO
<i>Ajuga L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000001061	Accepted (7 synonyms)
<i>Ballota L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000003972	Accepted (no synonyms)
<i>Calamintha Mill.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000005943	Synonym of <i>Clinopodium L.</i>
<i>Clinopodium L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000893668	Accepted (14 synonyms)
<i>Coleus Lour.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000008914	Accepted (21 synonyms)
<i>Cyclotrichium (Boiss.) Manden. & sceng.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000010295	Accepted (no synonyms)
<i>Eremostachys Bunge</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000013745	Synonym of <i>Phlomoides Moench</i>
<i>Hymenocrater Fisch. & C.A.Mey.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000018659	Accepted (1 synonyms)
<i>Lagochilus Bunge ex Benth.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000020447	Accepted (3 synonyms)
<i>Lallemantia Fisch. & C.A.Mey.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000020476	Accepted (1 synonyms)
<i>Lamium L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000020496	Accepted (8 synonyms)
<i>Lycopus L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000022514	Accepted (no synonyms)
<i>Marrubium L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000023200	Accepted (1synonyms)
<i>Melissa L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000023662	Accepted (1 synonyms)
<i>Mentha L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000023748	Accepted (5 synonyms)
<i>Micromeria Benth.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000024153	Accepted (7 synonyms)
<i>Moluccella L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000024596	Accepted (5 synonyms)
<i>Nepeta L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000025901	Accepted (11 synonyms)
<i>Ocimum L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000026511	Accepted (4 synonyms)
<i>Pentapleura Hand. - Mazz.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000028619	Accepted (no synonyms)
<i>Phlomis L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000029282	Accepted (4 synonyms)

<i>Prunella L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000031279	Accepted (2 synonyms)
<i>Salvia L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000033888	Accepted (58 synonyms)
<i>Sideritis L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000035314	Accepted (9 synonyms)
<i>Satureja L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000034152	Accepted (4 synonyms)
<i>Scutellaria L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000034856	Accepted (8 synonyms)
<i>Stachys L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000036243	Accepted (15 synonyms)
<i>Teucrium L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000038030	Accepted (17 synonyms)
<i>Tapeinanthus Herb.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000037547	Synonym of <i>Narcissus L.</i>
<i>Thymus L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000038335	Accepted (3 synonyms)
<i>Thymbra Mill.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-1200040137	Synonym of <i>Satureja L.</i>
<i>Vetix L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000040364	Accepted (21 synonyms)
<i>Ziziphora L.</i>	https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-4000041243	Accepted (2 synonyms)

All links were accessed on: (21 October 2022), (23 Dec 2023) and (10 October 2024).

Mentha longifolia, *Salvia splendens* and *Stachys tenuifolia* were reported as unchecked and waiting scrutiny till last the time of checking in this study (10 Oct 2024), the study marked them with yellow highlight color in table 3. While *Stachys alopecuroides*, *Mentha longifolia* var. *mollivima*, *Mentha silvestris*, *Ocimum vulgare* var. *viride*, *Ocimum vulgare*, *Ocimum majorana*, *Satureja bornmulleri*, *Scutellaria ballalodes*, *Scutellaria kochgam*, *Scutellaria katschy* and *Stachys alopecuroides* were not recorded in WFO and the study marked them with green highlight color in table 3. The species *Mentha piperita* was not recorded in WFO, but there was an accepted hybrid species named *Mentha x piperita* L. and another named *Mentha piperella* (Lej.) opiz ex Lej. & Courtois. (marked with blue highlight color in table 3) the specimens of its need to be examined again in BUH to identify this specimen correctly. According to [17] the genus *Vitex* L. is placed within the family Lamiaceae and the study found that there are 21 synonyms reported for it in WFO. (table 3)

Table 3 Taxonomic status of the species that reserved in some herbariums in Iraq

Genus	Species	Taxonomic status
Ajuga	<i>chamaepitys</i>	Accepted
	<i>oblongata</i>	Accepted
	<i>orientalis</i>	Accepted
	<i>tridactylites</i>	Accepted
	<i>vetita</i>	Accepted
	<i>aucheri</i>	Accepted
Ballota	<i>nigra</i>	Accepted
Calamintha	<i>rodundifolius</i>	The genus is a synonym (table 2)

	<i>exigua</i>	
	<i>florida</i>	
	<i>staminum</i>	
Clinopodium	<i>vulgare</i>	Accepted
Coleus	<i>blumei</i>	Synonym of <i>Coleus scutellarioides</i> (L.) Benth. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000913643
Cyclotrichium	<i>stamineum</i>	Accepted
Eremostachys	<i>laciniata</i>	The genus is a synonym (table 2)
	<i>macrophylla</i>	
Hymenocrater	<i>bituminosus</i>	Accepted
	<i>longiflorus</i>	Accepted
Lagochilus	<i>kotschyanus</i>	Accepted
Lallemantia	<i>iberica</i>	Accepted
	<i>peltata</i>	Accepted
	<i>royleana</i>	Accepted
lamium	<i>amplexicaule</i>	Accepted
	<i>crinitum</i>	Synonym of <i>Lamium album</i> subsp. <i>crinitum</i> (Montbret & A. Benth.) Mennema https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000222480
	<i>iranicum</i>	Unchecked and waiting taxonomic scrutiny https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000222559
	<i>stiatum</i>	Synonym of <i>Lamium garganicum</i> subsp. <i>stiatum</i> (Sm.) Hayek. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000222674
Lycopus	<i>europaeus</i>	Accepted
Marrubium	<i>astracanicum</i>	Accepted
	<i>crassidens</i>	Accepted
	<i>cuneatum</i>	Accepted
	<i>cuneatum</i> var. <i>spinulosum</i>	Synonym of <i>Marrubium cuneatum</i> Banks & Sol. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000811479
	<i>polyodont</i>	Synonym of <i>Marrubium ceatum</i> Banks & Sol. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000236670
	<i>vulgare</i>	Accepted
Melissa	<i>officinalis</i>	Accepted
Mentha	<i>longifolia</i> var. <i>incana</i>	Synonym of <i>Mentha longifolia</i> subsp. <i>Longifolia</i> https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000240950
	<i>longifolia</i> var. <i>mollivima</i>	Not reported in WFO
	<i>longifolia</i>	Unchecked and waiting taxonomic scrutiny https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000240918
	<i>spicata</i>	Accepted

	<i>arvensis</i>	Accepted
	<i>alopecuroides</i>	Synonym of <i>Mentha x villosa</i> Huds. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000241184
	<i>silvestris</i>	Not reported in WFO
	<i>piperita</i>	Reported as <i>Mentha x piperita</i> L. as an accepted name. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000241184 or it is <i>Mentha piperella</i> (Lej.) opiz ex Lej. & Courtois. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000241183
Micromeria	<i>mollis</i>	Synonym of <i>Clinopodium molle</i> (Benth.) Kuntze https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000243361
	<i>juliana</i>	Accepted
Moluceella	<i>laevis</i>	Accepted
Nepeta	<i>glandulosa</i>	Synonym of <i>Nepeta macrosiphon</i> Bross. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000250960
	<i>betonicifolia</i>	Accepted
	<i>hussknechtii bornm.</i>	Synonym of <i>Nepeta Racemosa</i> subsp. <i>haussknechtii</i> (Bornm.) A. L. Budantesv https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000250996
	<i>kurdica</i>	Accepted
	<i>humilis</i>	Accepted
	<i>iodantha</i>	Synonym of <i>Nepeta lamijifolia</i> Willd. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000251032
	<i>italica</i>	Accepted
	<i>kurdica</i>	Accepted
	<i>elymaitica</i>	Accepted
	<i>trachonitica</i>	Accepted
Ocimum	<i>basilicum</i>	Accepted
	<i>majorana</i>	Not reported in WFO
	<i>vulgare var. viride</i>	Not reported in WFO
	<i>vulgare</i>	Not reported in WFO
Pentapleura	<i>subulifera</i>	Accepted
Phlomis	<i>armeniaca</i>	Accepted
	<i>bruguieri</i>	Accepted
	<i>herba-venti</i>	Accepted
	<i>kudica</i>	Accepted
	<i>olivieri</i>	Accepted
	<i>praetervisa</i>	Accepted
	<i>rigida</i>	Accepted
	<i>lanceolata</i>	Accepted
Prunella	<i>valgaris</i>	Accepted

Salvia	<i>aegyptiaca</i>	Accepted
	<i>amasiaca</i>	Synonym of <i>Salvia verticillate</i> sbsp. <i>Amasiaca</i> (freyne & Bornm.) Bornm. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000302603
	<i>arabica</i>	Accepted
	<i>bracteata</i>	Accepted
	<i>candidissima</i>	Accepted
	<i>ceratophylla</i>	Accepted
	<i>compressa</i>	Accepted
	<i>centraversa</i>	Accepted
	<i>indica</i>	Accepted
	<i>kurdica</i>	Accepted
	<i>lanigera</i>	Accepted
	<i>multicaulis</i>	Accepted
	<i>montbretii</i>	Accepted
	<i>nemorosa</i>	Accepted
	<i>palaestina</i>	Accepted
	<i>poculata</i>	Accepted
	<i>russellii</i>	Accepted
	<i>sclarea</i>	Accepted
	<i>reuterana</i>	Accepted
	<i>macrosiphon</i>	Accepted
<i>spinosa</i>	Synonym of <i>Salvia nilotica</i> Juss. Ex Jacq. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000302355	
<i>splendens</i>	Unchecked and waiting taxonomic scrutiny http://www.worldfloraonline.org/taxon/wfo-0000302359 .	
<i>suffruticosa</i>	Accepted	
<i>syriaca</i>	Accepted	
<i>trichoclada</i>	Accepted	
<i>viridis</i>	Accepted	
<i>poculata</i>	Accepted	
Sideritis	<i>kurdica</i>	Synonym of <i>Sideritis libanotica</i> subsp. <i>kurdica</i> (Bornm.) Hub. - Mor. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000310208
	<i>montana</i>	Accepted
Satureja	<i>cuneifolia</i>	Accepted
	<i>macrantha</i>	Accepted
	<i>bornmulleri</i>	Not reported in WFO
Scutellaria	<i>bornmulleri</i>	Accepted
	<i>condensata</i>	Synonym of <i>Scutellaria albida</i> subsp. <i>condensata</i> (Rech.f.) J.R.Edm. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000307733

	<i>fruticosa</i>	Synonym of <i>Scutellaria tomentosa</i> Bertol. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000307826
	<i>megalaspis</i>	Accepted
	<i>ballaloides</i>	Not reported in WFO
	<i>kochgam</i>	Not reported in WFO
	<i>katschyi</i>	Not reported in WFO
27.Stachys	<i>megalodonta</i>	Accepted
	<i>tenuifolia</i>	Unchecked and waiting taxonomic scrutiny http://www.worldfloraonline.org/taxon/wfo-0000314676 .
	<i>cretica</i>	Accepted
	<i>kurdica</i>	Accepted
	<i>setifera</i>	Accepted
	<i>melampyroides</i>	Accepted
	<i>spectabilis</i>	Accepted
	<i>arvensis</i>	Accepted
	<i>alopecuroides</i>	Not reported in WFO
	<i>ballotiformis</i>	Synonym of <i>Stachys kurdica</i> subsp. <i>Kurdica</i> https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000313751
	<i>burgsdorffiodes</i>	Accepted
	<i>fragillima</i>	Accepted
	<i>graveolens</i>	Accepted
	<i>inflata</i>	Accepted
	<i>lanigera</i>	Accepted
	<i>iberica</i>	Accepted
<i>pubescens</i>	Synonym of <i>Stachys annua</i> subsp. <i>annua</i> https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000314454	
<i>kotschyi</i>	Accepted	
<i>lavandulifolia</i>	Accepted	
Tapeinanthus	<i>persicus</i>	The genus is synonym (table 2)
Teucrium	<i>chamaedrys</i>	Accepted
	<i>divaricatum</i>	Accepted
	<i>oliverianum</i>	Accepted
	<i>polium</i>	Accepted
	<i>parviflorum</i>	Accepted
	<i>melissoides</i>	Accepted
	<i>rigidum</i>	Accepted
	<i>procerum</i>	Accepted
<i>scordium</i>	Accepted	
Thymus	<i>kotschyanus</i>	Accepted

	<i>syriacus</i>	Accepted
Thymbra	<i>sintensisii</i>	The genus is synonym (table 2)
	<i>spicata</i>	
	<i>bovei</i>	
Vetix	<i>agnus</i>	Synonym of Vitex agnus- castus L. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000332915
	<i>pseudo</i>	Not reported in WFO
	<i>pseudonegudo</i>	Synonym of Vitex agnus- castus L. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000333382
Ziziphora	<i>acutifolia</i>	Synonym of Ziziphora tenuior L. https://list.worldfloraonline.org/wfo-0000335451
	<i>capitata</i>	Accepted
	<i>clinopodioides</i>	Accepted
	<i>tenuior</i>	Accepted

(Links were accessed on 10 Oct 2024 and the links of the acceptance names are the same of the genera in table 2)

4. Conclusion

The plant family Lamiaceae in Iraq include 139 species belonging to 33 genera. The study recommended that some of the plant specimens preserved in the herbarium mentioned in this study need to be re-identified in order to establish their taxonomic position correctly.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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